

Using Multiaxial Fatigue to Investigate the Anisotropic Performance of Additively Manufactured Material

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Combined axial-torsion loading

A majority of materials testing is based on uniaxial, planar stress states, but this can be a great simplification of real loading cases. This is often still adequate for design, but the analytical tools for multi-axial stress can also offer ways to extract more data.

Combining tension and torsion, on a tubular specimen, effectively rotates the direction of loading relative to the specimen axis.

Additive manufacture by polymer filament deposition, creates a laminated structure, so building in the specimen axis direction, and using Mohr's circle, we can assess the apparent tensile or shear strength behaviour at different orientation relative to the laminae.

tensile axial stress and torsional shear stress combine to form a total curve for maximum shear.

The results imply that the material exhibits higher shear strength and drawing capacity with decreasing shear biaxiality

Equipment availability

Multi-axial loading used to require specialised, custom test equipment, but for over 15 years now, combined axial-torsional fatigue load frames have been an off-the-shelf product and there are around 2000 machines installed worldwide, from multiple manufacturers.

Effects of rotating principal axes

Specimens were manufactured with a nominal outer gauge diameter 7.7 mm and wall thickness 0.8 mm, with parallel length of 20 mm, using a partially-optimised molten filament deposition process for PLA polymer, resulting in 100% density.

Using the combined loading approach, the apparent ultimate shear stress initially increases as the maximum shear angle is rotated away from 45° to the axis (pure tension).

When considering fatigue life, under multi-axial loading, ISO TR 121102 advises that this is most strongly related to the maximum shear amplitude applied.

Plotting a series of investigative S-N curves at different levels of maximum shear stress with different rotations relative to the axis, shows a similar slope, but significant uplift in fatigue strength with rotation away from simple tension.

Process and microstructure effects

Taking the fully dense material as a baseline, a number of replicates were run at several angles, to give a basic indication of variability. The scatter is very low in this initial study, and this is probably due to the choice to build specimens individually (some parallel investigations indicate multi-specimen builds can result in 2 or more distinct populations of fatigue strength).

Now with only a small sample of specimens using a "de-optimised" process (the default process settings recommended) it is immediately visible that there is a reduction in monotonic shear

strength. Note that the monotonic measurements were conducted at considerably higher strain rate, to provide a degree of comparability with that present in 3Hz fatigue loading waveforms.

However, when applying a waveform at R=0.1 with maximum shear stress at 75% of the monotonic strength, the fatigue life is rendered almost indistinguishable. Simple examination of the cross-section at moderate magnification, shows that the de-optimised specimen has considerable void between filament passes, thus reducing the true cross-section for stress. The fully-dense process, is not without some form of laminate structure either.

Further investigations are ongoing, including extending the sample for better statistical significance. It may also be valuable to consider a fracture mechanics approach to the analysis as Mode I - III mixity.